

Can methane pyrolysis based hydrogen production lead to the decarbonisation of iron and steel industry ?

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Abstract

Decarbonisation of the iron and steel industry would require the use of innovative low-carbon production technologies. Use of 100% hydrogen in a shaft furnace (SF) to reduce iron ore has the potential to reduce emissions from iron and steel production significantly. In this work, results from the techno-economic assessment of a H₂-SF connected to an electric arc furnace(EAF) for steel production are presented under two scenarios. In the first scenario H₂ is produced from molten metal methane pyrolysis in an electrically heated liquid metal bubble column reactor. Grid connected low-temperature alkaline electrolyser was considered for H₂ production in the second scenario. In both cases, 59.25 kgH₂ was required for the production of one ton of liquid steel (tls). The specific energy consumption (SEC) for the methane pyrolysis based system was found to be 5.16 MWh/tls. The system used 1.51 MWh/tls of electricity, and required 263 kg/tls of methane, corresponding to an energy consumption of 3.65 MWh/tls. The water electrolysis based system consumed 3.96 MWh/tls of electricity, at an electrolyser efficiency of 50 KWh/kgH₂. Both systems have direct emissions of 129.4 kgCO₂/tls. The indirect emissions are dependent on the source of natural gas, pellet making process and the grid-emission factor. Indirect emissions for the electrolysis based system could be negligible, if the electricity is generated from renewable energy sources. The levelized cost of production(LCOP) was found to be \$631, and \$669 respectively at a discount rate of 8%, for a plant-life of 20 years. The LCOP of a natural gas reforming based direct reduction steelmaking plant of operating under similar conditions was found to be \$414. Uncertainty analysis was conducted for the NPV and IRR values.

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1. Introduction

Global greenhouse gas(GHG) emissions need to be reduced by 45% by 2030 from 2010 levels and to net zero by 2050 to limit global mean temperature rise to 1.5°C [1]. Energy intensive industries (EII) like iron and steel, aluminum, cement, chemicals etc. are responsible for large share of the global GHG emissions. Decarbonisation of EII's is essential to achieve the 2050 emission reduction targets. Iron and steel production contributes to 7% of the global GHG emissions [2]. The use of demand reduction measures like material efficiency, material substitution and product service-life extension are important in achieving emission reductions from the steel industry [3]. However, in the short and medium term, as living standards improve in developing countries, the demand for steel could increase. The demand for primary steel is projected to increase by 30% in the next three decades [4]. At present majority of the primary steel is produced through the blast furnace-basic oxygen furnace(BF-BOF) route, where coke is used to reduce Fe_2O_3 to Fe in the BF and is converted to steel in the BOF. Approximately 1.8 ton(t) of CO_2 is released to produce ton of liquid steel (tls) [5]. An alternative production route is the reduction of solid Fe_2O_3 by a mixture of CO and H_2 in a direct reduction shaft furnace [6]. The direct reduced iron (DRI) could be processed in an electric arc furnace (EAF) to produce steel. The reducing gas is produced from reforming of natural gas or through coal gasification. The specific energy consumption (SEC) of a natural gas(NG) reforming based DRI-EAF systems varies from 2.9-3.5 MWh/tls, and direct emissions vary from 0.9 to 1.2 tCO_2/tls [7]. Efficiency improvement measures have reduced the energy and emission intensity of the steel industry in the past decades. However, complete decarbonisation of the iron and steel industry, while meeting the increasing steel demand, would require the introduction of innovative production technologies [8, 9].

Fishedick et al. evaluated the techno-economic feasibility of three innovative iron production technologies i.e. blast furnace with carbon capture and storage (CCS), low and high-temperature iron ore electrolysis (electrowining), and H_2 -direct reduction (DR) [10]. They found that H_2 -DR and electrolysis based production routes have the highest potential to decarbonise the steel industry in the future. A multi-criteria analysis of primary steelmaking technologies was conducted by Weigel

et al. [11]. Electrolysis and H_2 -DR were rated as the most promising technologies for low-carbon steel production. Toktarova et al. conducted a techno-economic pathway analysis for low-carbon transition of the Swedish steel industry. They found that H_2 -DR-EAF based steel production has the highest decarbonisation potential and could reduce total CO_2 emissions in Sweden by 10% [12]. Under the Ultra-Low Carbon Dioxide Steelmaking (ULCOS) research program, two iron-ore electrolysis processes were studied [13, 6]. These processes are still at lab-scale and are not expected to be available for commercial deployment before 2040, and are hence not included in this analysis [10]. DR of iron ore with 100% H_2 was carried out at commercial scale using fluidized-bed reactors at an industrial plant in Trinidad and Tobago in the early 1990's [14]. The plant produced steel with 95% metallization rate, at a production capacity of 65 ton of liquid steel per hour (tls/hr) in a shaft-furnace(SF) reactor [15]. Direct reduction with more than 90% H_2 was conducted by Energiron at a test facility in Hysla, Monterrey [16]. A H_2 -(SF) plant with an output capacity of one ton/day was commissioned under the HYBRIT project (consortium of Luossavaara-Kiirunavaara Aktiebolag (LKAB), Svenskt Stål AB (SSAB), and Vattenfall) in August 2020 in Sweden [17]. The project also aims to the develop a fossil fuel free pellet making process and a H_2 storage unit for continuous functioning of the plant. All major steel companies are involved in building industrial demonstration plants for H_2 -SF based plants [18, 19, 20, 21, 22]. The largest producers of DRI shaft furnaces, MIDREX and ENERGIRON, have indicated that their shaft furnace designs can be easily modified to use 100% H_2 as the reducing agent [23, 16].

H_2 required for steel production could be produced by water electrolysis or from fossil fuels like natural gas or coal. 95% of H_2 is produced by steam methane reforming (SMR) at present. However, SMR process has a high carbon-footprint, and it's continued use would be an obstacle in achieving the emission reduction goals. In recent times, the role of green H_2 produced from water electrolysis, using renewable electricity has become increasingly prominent in decarbonising the energy system. It has the potential to decarbonise hard-to-abate sectors like industries (steel, ammonia, methanol etc.), heavy transport, shipping and aviation [24]. Although renewable electricity powered water electrolysis produces emission-free H_2 , limited availability, and high-prices of renewable electricity are a deterrent to the large-scale deployment of industrial decarbonisation projects [2, 5]. For example, converting existing steel production units in the EU to H_2 -SF-EAF would require an additional 300-400 TWh/year of renewable electricity [25]. In the short and medium term, low-

carbon H_2 produced from natural gas could pave the way for industrial H_2 projects [23]. SMR coupled with carbon capture and storage (CCS) has been proposed as an alternative for low-carbon H_2 production. However, there are concerns about the cost, safety and social acceptability of CCS [26]. Another alternative for low-carbon H_2 production is methane pyrolysis, where CH_4 is decomposed to solid-carbon and CH_4 [27]. Methane pyrolysis could act as a bridge technology until large-amounts of cheap renewable electricity becomes available, while infrastructure and end-use applications are deployed [28]. Parkinson et al. evaluated the costs of carbon mitigation from a life-cycle perspective of 12 different hydrogen production technologies, and found methane pyrolysis as the most cost-effective short-term carbon abatement solution [29].

To the best of the knowledge of the authors, integration of methane pyrolysis with H_2 -SF-EAF system based steel production has not been evaluated previously. In this work, techno-economic assessment of H_2 -SF-EAF system based steel production has been conducted for two scenarios. Iron ore reduction is carried out in a H_2 -SF and an EAF is used for steelmaking in both cases. H_2 is produced from methane pyrolysis in the first scenario and water electrolysis in the second. The analysis was conducted to answer the following questions.

1. Is it techno-economically feasible to integrate methane pyrolysis with H_2 -SF-EAF system based steel making process?
2. How does methane pyrolysis compare with water electrolysis based H_2 -SF-EAF system system in terms of SEC, emissions, and economic parameters ?
3. Which factors have the maximum impact on the economic performance of H_2 -SF-EAF system based steel production systems in both the scenarios?

The rest of the paper is structured as following. A brief review of the literature is presented in Section 2. Section 3, describes the methodology used to develop the techno-economic assessment model. The modelling and simulation results of the analysis are presented in section 4. Discussions and inferences from the analysis are collated in section 5, followed by the conclusions in section 6.

2. Literature Review

Vogl et al. conducted a techno-economic analysis of H_2 -SF-EAF based steel production route, a low-temperature electrolyser(LTE) was used for hydrogen generation [30]. Their assessment

revealed that the production costs vary from €361-640 /t of steel, and is highly dependent on the price of electricity and the carbon emission prices. In a recent article, Krüger et al. analyzed the techno-economics of integrating a high-temperature electrolyser(HTE) to the H₂-SF-EAF system [31]. They calculated a 21% reduction in the energy consumption of a HTE based system. Some
90 researchers have evaluated the use of methanol produced from co-electrolysis of H₂O and CO₂ in the shaft furnace for steel production [32].

Methane pyrolysis is an endothermic reaction and requires high-temperatures (1273-1773 K) to achieve high-conversion rates. Solid-carbon, produced as a by-product of methane pyrolysis has many industrial applications, and could be sold at \$0.4/kg - \$2/kg to generate additional revenue
95 [33]. Excess unsold carbon could be stored in geological storage or unused coal mines [29]. It can be handled, transported and stored at a fraction of the cost of gaseous CO₂. Schneider et al. reviewed different technologies for production of H₂ from methane pyrolysis, thermal decomposition, plasma decomposition and catalytic decomposition. Keipi et al. compared the economic feasibility of hydrogen production by methane pyrolysis with SMR and water electrolysis. H₂ produced by
100 pyrolysis was found to have the lowest specific CO₂ emissions, and the economic feasibility was found to be dependent on the market price of solid-carbon [27]. Monolith materials has commissioned a methane pyrolysis plant in Nebraska, United states, primarily for carbon-black production [34]. They intend to use the by-product H₂ for industrial scale low-carbon ammonia production. The company uses plasma decomposition process powered by renewable electricity [35].

105 High-temperatures required for pyrolysis leads to complex reactor designs and higher costs. Thermo-catalytic reduction of CH₄ could lower the reaction temperature, leading to simpler reactor design. Metallic catalysts, carbonaceous catalysts like activated carbon and carbon black have been investigated previously for the production of H₂ from methane pyrolysis [36]. High-conversion rates were achieved at temperatures lower than 1273 K, but deposition of carbon on the surface of the catalysts
110 reduces their activity, and can clog the fluid-bed and packed-bed reactors used for thermo-catalytic conversion of CH₄ to H₂ and solid-carbon [37, 38, 39].

2.1. Molten metal methane pyrolysis

Molten metal pyrolysis, utilizes the low-density and insolubility of solid-carbon in liquids for effective separation of carbon, and could solve the problem of reactor clogging by carbon deposition [40]. CH₄

115 is passed through a molten metal in a liquid metal bubble column reactor(LMBR), decomposing
it to solid-carbon and H_2 . Serban et al. achieved a methane conversion of 57% using molten tin
in a LMBR at 1023 K [41]. Several experimental studies have recorded high-conversion rates, and
low-concentration of intermediate products [42, 43]. Upham et al. developed a conceptual process
model and evaluated the techno-economic feasibility of molten-metal methane pyrolysis [44]. They
120 proposed the use molten Fe as the heat transfer medium, and found the cost of H_2 to be comparable
to SMR-based H_2 production. Gregory et al. conducted an optimization-based techno-economic
analysis of an LMBR system to produce H_2 for an industrial boiler, and a petrochemical plant in
California [45]. They reported that in locations with high emission prices, levelized cost of H_2 could
be $\$0.39/\text{kgH}_2$, much lower than the cost of hydrogen produced from SMR, which varies $\$1.5\text{-}\2
125 $/\text{kgH}_2$. An industrial project to demonstrate molten-metal methane pyrolysis is being developed
jointly by Wintershall and Karlsruhe University of technology in Germany [46].

3. Methodology

The techno-economic assessment framework, developed for assessing green chemical technologies
at low technology readiness level (TRL) was used in this work [47]. Market demand and future
130 projections were assessed in the first step. Conceptual process models, and material and energy
balance models were developed to get preliminary estimates (30% accuracy) of the specific energy
demand, emissions, and component sizes in the second step. This was followed by an economic
analysis i.e. calculation of the NPV and IRR of the proposed production plants from an investor's
perspective. The final step involved conducting a sensitivity and uncertainty analysis, with NPV
135 and IRR as the target variables.

3.1. Market analysis and demand assessment

Steel demand is projected to increase by 30% in 2050 [4]. However, the market for low-carbon
steel technologies is not well-established. The recent policy shift towards decarbonisation of all
sectors of the economy, and emphasis on the use of climate-neutral industrial products could
140 increase the demand for low-carbon steel in the future [48, 49, 50]. Steel demand has traditionally
come from the infrastructure sector i.e. construction, shipping, power-generators etc. Achieving
a zero-carbon footprint across the value chain is becoming an important strategic objective for
different manufacturing industries i.e as the transport sector transitions from internal combustion

engines based vehicles to battery electric vehicles, the demand for low-carbon steel to manufacture
 145 automotive body parts could increase. Similarly, electricity sector’s transition from fossil fuel based
 power plants to wind and solar generators could lead to an increased demand for low-carbon steel.
 Iron and steel is used to build the wind tower structure, gearbox, generator and turbine transformers.
 The steel intensity of existing wind turbine models varies from 107 to 132 t/MW of installed capacity
 [51]. Solar photo-voltaic (PV) plants require 67.9 t/MW of steel [51]. According to estimates by
 150 the international renewable energy agency (IRENA), 6 Terawatt(TW) of wind and 9 TW of solar
 generators should be installed by 2050, increasing the share of renewable electricity generation to
 61% from the current 10% to limit the harmful impacts of anthropogenic climate change [52]. This
 target could translate into a huge demand for low-carbon steel.

3.2. Conceptual process modelling

155 Conceptual process models were developed for both scenarios to calculate the material and energy
 balances. Calculations are based on the production of one ton of liquid steel under steady state
 conditions. Integrated material and energy balance calculations were performed across the control
 volumes of major components of the proposed systems. The process schematics of the systems
 considered in scenario 1 and scenario 2, used for developing the models are presented in Figure 1a
 160 and Figure 1b respectively. The steel production process can be divided into three sub-processes i.e.
 production of reducing agent (hydrogen), iron production in the shaft furnace, and conversion of iron
 to steel in the EAF. The conceptual process flow diagram for the iron and steel production process
 using a shaft furnace and an EAF, is similar to the ones proposed by [30, 17, 5]. The difference in
 the overall material and energy balance of the two systems is attributed to the hydrogen production
 165 sub-process. Material flow through the components was evaluated using stoichiometric values of the
 reactants and products. It is assumed that the reactions reach completion in a single-pass, unless it
 is stated otherwise. The specific heat and enthalpy of the different species were calculated using the
 Shomate equation, as described in Equation 1 and 2. The coefficients of the Shomate equations
 were taken from NIST webBook [53].

$$C_p^\circ = A + B * t + D * t^2 + D * t^3 + E/t^2 \quad (1)$$

$$H^\circ - H^\circ_{298.15} = A * t + B * t^2/2 + D * t^3/3 + D * t^4/4 - E/t + F - H \quad (2)$$

170 *3.2.1. Iron production in the shaft furnace*

The shaft furnace is a counter current flow reactor [54]. The iron ore pellet enter the shaft furnace from the top, through the stream **M1** at ambient temperature. Impurities have an adverse impact on the reaction kinetics, and should be limited to less than 5% [55]. The impurities are primarily composed of Al_2O_3 and SiO_2 . The iron ore pellets react with the hydrogen gas , which enters the shaft furnace from the bottom of the furnace at 1173 K, represented by **M4**. The reduction of iron oxide to metallic iron occurs in three steps, where hematite (Fe_2O_3) is reduced to magnetite(Fe_3O_4), followed by magnetite’s reduction to wustite(FeO), and subsequently to metallic Fe. The reduction steps are presented in the Equations 3, 4 and 5. The heat of the reaction under standard conditions is 99.5 kJ/mol [56].

180 The reduction of Fe_2O_3 by H_2 is a non-catalytic, heterogeneous solid-gas endothermic reaction, where the overall reaction rate is dependent on the heat and mass transfer phenomena, and the rate of chemical reaction [57]. At higher temperatures, the chemical reaction rate increases exponentially, and diffusion of hydrogen through the laminar layer of hematite pellet is the rate limiting step [58]. Detailed analysis of the parameters affecting the overall reaction kinetics can be found in the literature [59, 57, 58, 60].

185 Metallization rate of 94% is achieved in the H_2 -SF [59]. The reduced iron exits the shaft furnace through stream **M2**, which is composed of metallic iron, wustite and impurities. The stream **M2** could be charged to the EAF at 873 K through the HOTLINK[®] or HYTEMP[®] process developed by MIDREX and ENERGIRON technologies respectively [61, 62]. Energy consumed for the transfer of hot-metal to the EAF has not been considered in the present model. Although it’s difficult to implement a hot-metal transport system in an existing steel plant, arrangements for gravity based transfer of hot-metal could be included in the design phase of a greenfield plant. The unreacted

hydrogen, and steam produced as a by-product of the reduction reaction exit the reactor through the exhaust stream, **M5**, at 573 K [31]. A condenser is used to separate hydrogen, and water from
195 the exhaust stream. Electrical resistance heaters are used to supply thermal energy to the shaft furnace.

3.2.2. Steel production in an EAF

The EAF is charged with 100% hot-DRI, and is heated to 1923 K. It exits the EAF, through the stream **M3**. The value of **M3** is fixed to one ton. Carbon fines of biogenic origin are added to
200 the EAF through the stream **M6**. Carbon is required for the conversion of iron to steel, reduction of wustite to iron, and for the formation of CO. CO promotes froth formation, which is crucial for effective slag removal. The presence of CO gas improves the overall heat transfer rate from the graphite electrodes to the melt. It is assumed that 20 kg/tls of carbon is added [63]. Slag formers, **M7**, (mixture of CaO and MgO) are added to remove impurities, and to increase the life
205 of the refractory lining of the furnace [64]. The slag exits the EAF through **M8**. The exhaust gases, composed primarily of CO₂, O₂ and N₂, exit the EAF through stream **M9** at 1773 K. Assumptions related to the air -infiltration, graphite electrode consumption etc. were taken from the literature [63].

Thermal energy is supplied by the electric arc formed between the graphite electrodes, and exothermic
210 oxidation reactions. The reduction reactions of FeO and C, and the reaction between carbon and O₂ have been considered in the present model. The reactions are presented in Equations 6,7, and 8 respectively. An electrical efficiency of 0.85 has been considered for the EAF to account for losses from the transformer, rectifier, electrodes, radiative and convective heat transfer etc. Kirschen et al. presented a similar approach to calculate the energy consumption of an EAF [64].

215 3.2.3. Scenario 1: LMBR subsystem

Catalan et al. designed an LMBR system for the production of 200 kta⁻¹ using a coupled hydrodynamic and kinetic model [65]. Molten tin was used as the heat transfer medium in the LMBR and ten different configurations of the LMBR were presented by the authors. Configuration with the highest conversion factor, and smallest volume was evaluated in this model. The mass flow rates of H₂, CH₄, solid-carbon were converted to the mass flows per ton of liquid steel (kg/tls). LMBR dimensions and operational parameters are presented in Table 1. Thermodynamic properties of liquid tin were calculated using correlation provided by [66], and are presented in Equation 9. The correlation is valid in the temperature range of $800 \leq T \leq 3000K$. The density of liquid tin was calculated using Equation 10 [67].

$$\Delta H = -1285.372 + 28.4512 * T \quad (9)$$

$$\rho_{tin} = C_3 - C_4(T - T_{ref}) \quad (10)$$

Where $C_3=6979 \text{ kgm}^{-3}$, $C_4=0.652 \text{ kgm}^{-3}\text{K}^{-1}$, and $T_{ref} = 505.08 \text{ K}$ is the melting point of tin. Equation 10 is valid in the temperature range of $506 \leq T \leq 1950 \text{ K}$.

Natural gas (100% CH₄) enters the system through the stream **M0**, at high pressure and ambient temperature. It is pre-heated in the heat recovery heat exchanger (HEX) by the stream **M11**, which
 220 is a mixture of H₂ and unreacted CH₄ exiting the LMBR at 1443 K. The stream **M11** exits the heat exchanger as **M12** at 1173 K. CH₄ is separated in the pressure swing adsorber(PSA), and exits as stream **M14**. The stream **M13** and **M14** are mixed and enter the carbon-bed at an elevated temperature, through the stream **M15**. The carbon-bed can be visualized as a solid-gas tubular heat exchanger [44]. The stream **M15** is heated to 973 K by the incoming stream of solid-carbon(**M16**).
 225 **M10**, enters the LMBR from the bottom, where a sparger disperses the pressurised gas into bubbles. Gas bubbles rise through the LMBR . They contain the solid-carbon particles, H₂, and CH₄ inside them, which are released at the top of the liquid tin surface. Molten metal acts as a heat transfer medium, providing heat for the endothermic decomposition of methane. The low-density carbon is insoluble in liquid tin, it can be readily removed in a continuous process in a manner similar to a
 230 floatation cell as is done routinely in slag removal. LMBR is made of 120 mm stainless steel, and is lined with a refractory layer of 600 mm, made of MgO bricks to sustain the high-temperatures inside the reactor [38]. An EAF is used for melting tin, and providing thermal energy to the LMBR [44].

Table 1: The reactor dimensions (M), temperature($^{\circ}$ C), pressure, conversion factors (%), methane feed rate (kg/s) have been taken from [65]

Length	Diameter	Volume(Tin)	Temperature	Pressure	Conversion factor	CH ₄ feed	H ₂ flow
m	m	Tons	K	Bar	percentage	kg/hr	ton/hr
8.66	5.21	850	1443	19	0.90	29.39	24.03

3.2.4. Scenario 2: Water electrolysis for hydrogen production

H₂ is produced using a low-temperature alkaline electrolyser, consuming 50 KWh/kgH₂. The hydrogen stream, **M17** exiting the electrolyser is pre-heated in the heat recovery heat exchanger to **M18**. Heat is recovered from the shaft-furnace exhaust stream, **M5**, in the heat exchanger. An electrical heater is used to raise the temperature of the stream **M18** to the 1173 K. The shaft-furnace exhaust gases enter the condenser through the stream **M19**, lowering it's temperature from 393 K to 343 K. Purified condensed water enters the electrolyser through the stream **M20**. Additional water requirements are met through the stream **M22**, to account for losses in the circuit. O₂ is produced as a by-product of the water-electrolysis and exits the electrolyser through the stream **M21**.

(a) Scenario 1 : H_2 -SF-EAF system, H_2 is produced in a liquid metal bubble column reactor(LMBR), through methane pyrolysis. The heat is supplied by an EAF.

(b) Scenario 2: H_2 -SF-EAF system, H_2 is produced by water electrolysis in a low-temperature alkaline electrolyser.

3.3. Economic evaluation

Preliminary sizing of the main process equipment (reactors, pressure vessels, EAF) was done for a 3.35 Mta⁻¹) steel production plant, which is comparable to the size of NG-reformer based DRI-EAF plants in operation [68]. H₂ production capacity of 200 kta⁻¹ was considered in both scenarios. Preliminary costs of the main process equipment were converted to the total capital costs using Lang factors from Sinnott [69]. The H₂-SF-EAF system plants were modelled as first-of-its-kind plants. A Lang-factor of five was considered for the H₂-SF-EAF system system, while a Lang factor of ten was used for the LMBR based hydrogen production system. The operational costs are comprised of the cost of iron ore, electricity, natural gas, and shaft furnace and EAF operational costs. A fixed price of electricity has been used to calculate the financial parameters for the plant. Only the direct emissions from the plants were used to evaluate the annual emissions cost. The annual maintenance cost was considered to be 2% of the capital cost, and a labour cost of 20\$/tls was considered in the model [69]. The levelized cost of production (LCOP) was calculated for both scenarios by considering the annualized capital, operational, labour, maintenance, and emission costs of the system, using Equation 11 and 12.

$$LCOP = \frac{C_{capex} * ACC + C_{opex} + C_{maint} + C_{labour} + C_{emission}}{Annual\ steel\ production} \quad (11)$$

$$ACC = \frac{r * (1 + r)^n}{(1 + r)^n - 1} \quad (12)$$

A discounted cash flow analysis was conducted to compare the NPV and IRR of the investment. NPV was calculated using Equation 13. IRR is calculated as the discount rate at which the NPV of the cash flow is zero. The salvage value of the equipment after the end of plant life was assumed to be zero, and a linear depreciation rate has been considered. A tax rate of 25% was assumed for the calculations.

$$NPV = \sum_{n=1}^n \frac{CF}{(1 + r)^n} \quad (13)$$

Where, ACC, CF, r, and n refer to the annuity factor, cumulative cash flow, discount rate, and the project life respectively. The economical parameters used for the calculations are presented in Table

250 2.

Revenue is generated from the sale of steel and by-products. Solid-carbon and oxygen are produced as a by-products of methane pyrolysis and water electrolysis respectively. Both by-products could be sold to generate additional revenue. Solid-carbon produced during methane pyrolysis is used in the manufacturing industries i.e. automobile tires, graphite electrodes, printer ink pigments, graphite electrodes etc. [27]. O₂ has many industrial applications. Assumptions related to the costs, and revenue used in the model are presented in Table 3.

Table 2: Economical parameters considered for the H₂-SF-EAF system system

Plant life	Plant construction	Discount rate	Tax rate	Depreciation	Steel output	H ₂ output
Years	Years	%	%	N.A	Mt/year	Kt/year
20	2	8	25	linear	3.07	200

Table 3: Assumptions used in the techno-economic assessment model

Capital cost assumptions			
Equipment	Cost(\$)	Lifetime	Reference/remark
Electrolyser (Million \$/MW H ₂)	0.704	90000 hours	[70]
Stack replacement (Million \$/MW H ₂)	0.540	100000 hours	[70]
Shaft furnace (\$t ⁻¹ DRI/year)	240	20 years	[31]
Electric arc furnace (\$t ⁻¹ steel/year)	140	20 years	[31]
Operational cost assumptions			
Item	Cost	Unit	Reference/remark
Iron ore	90	\$/t	[71]
Electricity	56	\$/MWh	[72]
Natural gas	6.58	\$/MMBTU	[72]
DRI OPEX	12	\$/tls	[73]
EAF OPEX	33	\$/tls	[73]
CO ₂ emission	35	\$/tCO ₂	[74]
Revenue stream assumptions			
Product	Price	Unit	Reference/remark
Carbon steel	700	\$/t	[71]
Carbon	200	\$/t	[44]
Oxygen	40	\$/t	Market price of O ₂

3.4. Sensitivity and uncertainty analysis

There are different sources of uncertainty in the model inputs. They arise from the fluctuations in the price of internationally traded commodities (iron ore, natural gas, carbon price etc.), and price of input parameters such as electricity cost, emission costs. The technologies analyzed in this work are at low TRL, hence values of input parameters such as electrolyser efficiency and cost are uncertain. Local and global sensitivity analysis were conducted to apportion the uncertainty in the model output to different model inputs [75]. The NPV and IRR of the system were selected as the target variables. In the first step a local parametric sensitivity analysis was conducted [76]. The input parameters (uncertain factors) were varied by $\pm 20\%$ from their base values, and percentage change in the output values were evaluated.

A global sensitivity analysis was conducted using the sobol sensitivity indices approach to ascertain the uncertainty of the NPV and IRR values, based on the global uncertainty in the input parameter values [77]. Sobol sensitivity analysis determines the contribution of each input parameter, and their interactions to the overall model output variance. The global sensitivity analysis was carried out using the SALib library to evaluate the Sobol first-order and Sobol total-order sensitivity indices [78]. The selected input parameters, and their lower and upper bounds are provided in Table 4.

Table 4: Lower and upper bounds of input parameters used for the global sensitivity analysis

Target Parameters : NPV and IRR			
Parameter	Lower bound	Upper bound	Unit
Tax rate	25	35	Percentage
Interest rate	0.06	0.12	Percentage
Electricity price	20	60	USD/MWh
Natural gas price	4	10	USD/MMBTU
Iron ore cost	75	120	USD/ton
Emission cost	35	200	Euro/tCO ₂
Carbon steel price	600	700	USD/ton
Carbon price	100	300	USD/ton
Electrolyser efficiency	45	60	KWh/kgH ₂
Electrolyser capital cost	0.2	0.7	Million \$/MWH ₂

4. Results

This section outlines the results of the techno-economic assessment. The material and energy balance, specific energy consumption, emissions, economic parameters, and results of the local and global sensitivity analysis are presented.

4.1. Material and energy balance

The material and energy flows through the different components of the steel production systems in presented in Table 5. It has been divided into three sub-processes as described in Section 3.2. The streams **M1** to **M9** represent the iron and steel production sub-process. Material and energy flows through the LMBR based H_2 production sub-system are presented by the streams **M0**, and **M10** to **M16**. The streams **M17** to **M22** depict the material and energy flows through the electrolyser based hydrogen production subsystem.

Approximately 59 kg of H_2 is required for the reduction of 1.5 ton of iron ore, required for one ton of steel production, considering a metallization rate of 94%, and impurity content of 5% in the iron ore pellets. Stoichiometric requirement of H_2 for iron oxide reduction is 54 kg/tls (considering 100% conversion of FeO in the EAF). A higher quantity of H_2 is considered in this model to account for 10% losses, owing to leakage, dissolution in water and other solid streams. The H_2 requirement is similar to the ones reported in the literature [31, 30, 25, 5]. For the methane pyrolysis based system 261.6 kg of CH_4 is required, resulting in the production of 178 kg of solid-carbon as a by-product. In the electrolyser based system, the stream **M18** is heated to the shaft furnace temperature of 1173 K.

Table 5: Material and energy flows through the different components of the steel production systems, considering a metallization rate of 0.94 and an impurity content of 5% in the iron ore pellets. Reaction enthalpy values are not presented in this table. More details about the calculations can be found in the Jupyter notebooks [79]

Stream	Description	Mass flow in kg/tls	Temperature in K	Enthalpy in KWh/tls
Shaft furnace -Electric arc furnace subsystem				
M1	Fe ₂ O ₃ pellets and impurities	1527.91	298	0.00
M2	Fe, FeO, and impurities	1089.48	873	99.02
M3	Liquid steel	1000.00	1923	324.84
M4	H ₂ stream (reducing gas)	59.25	1173	211.99
M5	Shaft furnace exhaust	489.31	573	76.65
M6	Carbon fines	20.00	298	0.00
M7	Slag formers	50	298	0.00
M8	EAF slag stream	126.39	1923	75.07
M9	EAF exhaust stream	230.00	1173	105.22
M _{air}	Infiltrated air	250.00	298	0.00
Liquid metal bubble column reactor subsystem				
M0	Natural gas from pipeline	263.37	298	0.00
M10	Pre-heated methane	263.37	973	166.07
M11	H ₂ and CH ₄ at LMBR outlet	85.38	1443	316.48
M12	H ₂ and CH ₄ from HEX	85.38	1173	235.20
M13	Pre-heated incoming CH ₄ stream	263.37	585	83.96
M14	CH ₄ stream from PSA	26.12	1173	23.17
M15	Mixed CH ₄ stream	263.37	616	96.33
M16	Carbon stream from LMBR	177.77	1443	100.37
Electrolysis subsystem				
M17	H ₂ from electrolyser	59.56	343	1.12
M18	Heated H ₂	59.56	448	31.85
M19	H ₂ O after HEX	486.82	393	25.47
M20	Condensed H ₂ O	481.43	343	85.85
M21	O ₂ from electrolyser	476.49	343	6.63
M22	H ₂ O for electrolysis	52	298	0.0

4.2. Specific energy consumption

Both systems were assumed to be connected to the electricity grid, and all energy requirements of
295 the plants (except CH_4 used in the LMBR) were met by grid-electricity. The SF and the EAF have
a combined electricity consumption of 0.79 MWh/tls. The endothermic reduction of Fe_2O_3 in the
shaft furnace results in an additional electrical energy demand of 0.252 MWh/tls ($\eta = 0.85$). The
EAF uses 0.537 MWh/tls ($\eta = 0.8$) of electricity. The total electricity requirements are higher than
the NG-reformer based DRI-EAF unit, which requires approximately 0.680 MWh/tls. Thermal
300 energy demand in the NG-reformer based DRI units is met by the exothermic reaction between CO
and Fe_2O_3 .

In scenario one, the SEC was found to be 5.16 MWh/tls. CH_4 entering the reactor is pre-heated
to 973 K by exchanging heat with the streams **M11**, **M16** and **M14**. 55% of the thermal energy
contained in the solid-carbon stream, **M16**, is recovered. The LMBR consumes 0.71 MWh/tls of
305 electricity at an EAF efficiency of 80 %, which is slightly higher than 0.51 MWh/tls ((reported as
31 MJ/kg H_2) calculated by Upham et al for a similar system [44]. They considered 90% sensible
heat recovery from the H_2 stream exiting the reactor and solid-carbon stream, along with an EAF
efficiency of 90 % leading to slightly lower electricity consumption. In addition, CH_4 used in LMBR
as a chemical feedstock, corresponds to an energy consumption of 3.65 MWh/tls at lower heating
310 value of 48 MJ/kg of CH_4 . The SEC of a NG-reformer based DRI-EAF system is much lower at
3.26 MWh/tls [16].

The water electrolysis based H_2 -SF-EAF system system has an SEC of 3.96 MWh/tls, at an
electrolyser efficiency of 50 KWh/kg H_2 . Electrolysers consume 2.96 MWh/tls or 74.7% of the total
electricity. The H_2 stream, exiting the electrolyser is pre-heated by exchanging heat with the SF
315 exhaust gases. It exits the heat exchanger at a 448 K. The H_2 stream is subsequently heated to the
reactor temperature of 1173 K °C in an electrical heater consuming 0.211 MWh/tls of electricity
($\eta = 0.85$). In the literature, the SEC value of comparable systems vary from 3.48 MWh/tls [30, 17]
to 3.95 MWh/tls [31]. The difference in the SEC's originate from the use of different values of
electrolyser efficiency (depends on the projected installation year of the plant), use of scrap in the
320 EAF, thermal energy requirements of the shaft-furnace, purge-gas requirements etc. The energy
consumption of the different components for both scenarios is depicted in Figure 2a, and Figure 2b.

(a) Energy consumption of the methane pyrolysis based H₂-SF-EAF system system

(b) Energy consumption of the electrolyser based H₂-SF-EAF system system

Figure 2

4.3. Emissions

4.3.1. Direct emissions

Direct emissions of 129.4 kgCO₂/t_{ls} have been considered for both scenarios, which are related to
325 CO₂ emissions from the EAF. The EAF emissions originate from the use of carbon fines, graphite
electrodes and the production of lime.

4.3.2. Indirect emissions

The indirect emissions are related to the use of electricity and natural gas. The pellet making process
accounts for the release of 120 kgCO₂/t_{ls} of emissions. In the HYBRIT project, new production
330 methods are being developed to decarbonise the pellet making process [17]. An upstream emission of
17 gCO₂/MJ has been considered for natural gas, taking into account the fugitive emissions caused
by production, transport and distribution of natural gas [80]. Indirect emissions associated with
electricity use are dependent on the electricity mix of the region, and is represented by the grid
emission factor (GEF) [81].

335 4.3.3. Total emissions

The total emissions were calculated as the sum of the direct and indirect emissions. Considering a
GEF of 412 kgCO₂/MWh, corresponding to the GEF of EU-28 [81]. The total emissions in scenario
one were 0.90 tCO₂/t_{ls}. The value is comparable to the emissions of 0.98 tCO₂/t_{ls} from a reforming
based NG-DRI-EAF system. More natural gas is consumed in the LMBR, for the production of
340 reducing agent (H₂) resulting in a higher amount of indirect upstream emissions. The impact of
variation in the GEF on emissions for LMBR system is depicted in Figure 3a.

The total emissions from the electrolyser based H₂-SF-EAF system system were found to be 1.93
tCO₂/t_{ls}. In countries with cleaner electricity mix, the total emissions for electrolyser based H₂-SF-
EAF system system were found to be much lower than NG-reformer based DRI-EAF systems. If
345 electricity is supplied from renewable energy generators, the total emissions in the second scenario
could be much lower, as can be seen in Figure 3b from the lower emissions in Norway and Sweden.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3: (a) Direct and indirect emissions from the methane pyrolysis based H₂-SF-EAF system. (b) Direct and indirect emissions from the electrolysis based H₂-SF-EAF system. The grey band on the top of chart depicts the range of emissions from BF-BOF based steel production. The black dots represent the total emissions a NG-reformer based DRI-EAF system.

4.4. Economic analysis

The methane pyrolysis based system has a lower LCOP of 631 \$/t, compared to the LCOP of 669 \$/t for the electrolyser based H₂-SF-EAF system. The LCOP value is at the higher end of values reported in the literature, as we have considered first-of-its kind plants, resulting in higher capital costs [30, 31]. Additionally, we have considered maintenance, labour and emission costs in LCOP calculations, which were not included in the previous studies. The NG reformer based DRI-EAF system has a much lower LCOP of 414 \$/t. The break-up of the LCOP is presented in Figure 4. The annual operational costs contribute to more than 50% of the production costs in all three scenarios. Annualized capital costs have a significant contribution to the LCOP of methane pyrolysis based system. Compared to the low-carbon steel production routes, emission costs have the highest impact on the production costs of the NG reformer based DRI-EAF system. In a carbon constrained world, rising emission prices could increase production costs significantly for the NG reformer based DRI-EAF systems.

Figure 4: Breakup of levelized cost of production of steel for both scenarios. The costs are compared with an NG reformer based DRI-EAF based system, operating under similar conditions.

360 *4.5. Discounted cash flow analysis*

A discounted cash flow analysis was conducted for both the scenarios, under the economical assumptions presented in Table 2 and Table 3. The NPV was \$1.07 billion for the first scenario, and \$-5 million in the second scenario. At 10.01 %, the IRR of the methane pyrolysis based steelmaking unit was higher than the discount rate of 8%. The IRR of the electrolyser based H₂-SF-EAF system based steelmaking unit was found to be 7.98 %. A NG reformer based DRI-EAF system operating under the same conditions was found to have an NPV of \$5.9 billion, and an IRR of 33.1%.

4.5.1. Local sensitivity analysis

The results of the local sensitivity analysis reveal that the NPV of the methane pyrolysis based H₂-SF-EAF system system are highly sensitive to changes in the carbon steel price and discount rate. The IRR of the system is sensitive to the carbon steel price, and the iron ore costs. The other significant factors are the electricity prices, and the natural gas price. The NPV and IRR of the electrolyser based H₂-SF-EAF system system are sensitive to changes in the carbon steel price, electricity cost, and the electrolyser efficiency. The results of the sensitivity analysis are presented in Figure 5a, 5b, 6a, and 6b.

375 *4.5.2. Global sensitivity analysis*

The results of the global sensitivity analysis in the form of first order Sobol indices, and total order Sobol indices are presented in Figure 7a and Figure 7b. The values of the second order Sobol indices were found to be insignificant, indicating weak interaction between the input variables. It can be inferred that the interest rate, and carbon steel price have maximum contribution to the variance of methane pyrolysis system's NPV. The variance in the IRR value of the methane pyrolysis system stems from the uncertainty in carbon steel price, electricity price, and the cost of emissions. Variations in electricity cost, and carbon steel price can be attributed with the maximum contribution to the variance in the NPV and IRR values of the electrolyser based system.

(a)

(b)

Figure 5: The sensitivity of different parameters with NPV (a) Scenario one (b) Scenario two

(a)

(b)

Figure 6: The sensitivity of different parameters with IRR (a) Scenario one (b) Scenario two

(a)

(b)

Figure 7: (a) First order and total order Sobol indices calculated to quantify the uncertainty propagation in NPV and IRR values of the methane pyrolysis based H₂-SF-EAF system system. (b) First order and total order Sobol indices calculated to quantify the uncertainty propagation in NPV and IRR values of the water electrolyser based H₂-SF-EAF system system.

5. Discussion

385 Economic feasibility of the LMBR system is highly sensitive to the discount rate, owing to the higher capital costs of the system. The total capital cost of the methane pyrolysis based system was found to be \$7.1 billion. LMBR system capex was \$743 million and the H₂-SF-EAF system had a capex of \$6.4 billion. Capital costs of the H₂-SF-EAF system steelmaking unit could reduce in the future as new plants are installed. The use of EAF for heating the LMBR has a major contribution to the
390 LMBR capital costs. Tank-lined electric resistive heating elements made of silicon carbide could heat the reactor and lead to reduction in LMBR system costs [45]. The capital costs of the LMBR could be reduced by using a cheaper heat-transfer metal, or by using catalytic metals to lower the reaction temperature [82].

The operational costs of the electrolyser based system have the highest impact on the economic
395 feasibility. The operational costs could be reduced by selecting regions with low electricity prices for installation of the plant. Improvements in the electrolyser efficiency could also reduce the operational costs. Using solid oxide electrolysers (SOEC) for H₂ generation could reduce the electricity consumption, by utilizing heat from the shaft-furnace exhaust gases for steam generation [31]. Waste heat recovery from the EAF exhaust gases to heat the iron ore pellets could reduce
400 the energy consumption, as they leave the EAF at 1773 K. Integration of renewable generators, with optimally sized electrolysers, and H₂ storage could allow the use of cheap renewable electricity for steelmaking [83]. Additional revenue generated by providing demand-response services to the electricity grid could also lower the cost of operation of the plants in the future by producing and storing large quantities of H₂ during times of low-electricity prices. However, availability of geological
405 storage in close proximity to the steel production facilities is integral to leveraging the variations in the electricity prices as other storage alternatives are quite expensive.

6. Conclusion

A techno-economic assessment was conducted to evaluate the viability of integrating methane pyrolysis for H₂-SF-EAF system based low-carbon steel production. The assessment was conducted
410 under two scenarios, and the results were compared. In the first scenario, hydrogen is produced by methane pyrolysis in a liquid metal bubble column reactor, and by low- temperature water electrolysis in the second scenario. The analysis was conducted from an investor's perspective

for first-of-its-kind plants, leading to higher capital costs. In scenario one, the specific energy consumption was 5.15 MWh/tls, comprising of 1.37 MWh/tls of electricity, and 3.65 MWh/tls of natural gas consumption. In scenario two, 3.96 MWh/tls of electricity was consumed. The direct emission in both cases were found to be 128 kg/tls. Total emissions for electrolyser based steel production were found to be lower in regions with a cleaner electricity mix. The levelized costs of production were found to be \$659 and \$651 respectively, which are higher than the production costs from a reformer based NG-DRI-EAF system. The main results of the techno-economic assessment are presented in Table 6.

Table 6: Results from the techno-economic assessment analysis

	SEC	Direct Emissions	CAPEX	OPEX	LCOP	NPV	IRR
Units	MWh/tls	KgCO ₂ /tls	\$ Billion	\$ Billion	\$	\$ Billion	%
LMBR-H ₂ -SF-EAF	5.16	129.42	7.15	1.17	631	1.07	10.09
Electrolyser-H ₂ -SF-EAF	3.96	129.42	6.6	1.38	669	-0.005	7.98
NG-DRI-EAF	3.26	541	2.56	0.95	414	5.9	33.1

Integrating methane pyrolysis with an H₂-SF-EAF system system is techno-economically feasible and could play an important role in decarbonising steel production in the short and medium term. The authors recommend the development of a consortium of steel companies, natural gas companies, researchers, and universities to further develop the technology, especially in regions with access to cheap natural gas and clean grid electricity.

7. Data availability

The software codes developed for the analysis are hosted on Zenodo. The model is written in the Python programming language [79].

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9. Abbreviations

Following abbreviations were used in the manuscript :

H ₂ -SF-EAF	Hydrogen-shaft furnace-electric arc furnace
DRI-EAF	Direct reduced iron-electric arc furnace
BF-BOF	Blast furnace-Basic oxygen furnace
SMR	Steam methane reforming
CCS	Carbon capture and storage
DR	Direct reduction
GHG	Green house gas
EII	Energy intensive industry
LTE	low-temperature electrolyser
HTE	High-temperature electrolyser
SMR	Steam methane reforming
BASF	Badische Anilin und Soda Fabrik
SSAB	Svenskt Stål AB
LKAB	Luossavaara-Kiirunavaara Aktiebolag
LMBR	Liquid metal bubble column reactor
PSA	Pressure swing adsorber
EAF	Electric arc furnace
HEX	Heat exchanger
SF	Shaft furnace
TRL	Technology readiness level
TDM	Thermal decomposition of methane
SEC	Specific energy consumption
MWh	Megawatt hour
KWh	Kilowatt hour
kJ	Kilojoule
MJ	Megajoule
MMBTU	Metric Million British Thermal Unit
\$	US dollar

tls	Ton of liquid steel
kg	Kilogram
kgH ₂	Kilogram of hydrogen
kt	Kiloton
Mt/y	Million ton per year
t	ton
кта ⁻¹	Kiloton per annum
tCO ₂	Ton of carbon dioxide
K	Kelvin
°C	Celsius
CF	Cash flow
NPV	Net present value
IRR	Internal rate of return
LCOP	Levellized cost of production
ACC	Annualized capacity factor or annuity factor
capex	Capital expenditure
opex	Operational expenditure
GEF	Grid emission factor
H ₂	Hydrogen
O ₂	Oxygen
H ₂ O	Water
CH ₄	Methane
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide
CO	Carbon Monoxide
N ₂	Nitrogen
Fe	Iron
FeO	Iron oxide
Fe ₂ O ₃	Iron oxide (Hematite)
Fe ₃ O ₄	Iron oxide (Magnetite)
Al ₂ O ₃	Alumina
SiO ₂	Silica

CaO	Calcium oxide (lime)
MgO	Magnesium oxide
NG	Natural gas

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